

NetXRate: O-RAN enabled network assisted rate control for XR services

Alejandro Lopez Garcia, Amr A. AbdelNabi, Daniel Camps-Mur, Miguel Catalan-Cid, Mario Montagud

i2CAT Foundation

Barcelona, Spain

Email: {alejandro.lopez, amr.abdelnabi, daniel.camps, miguel.catalan, mario.montagud}@i2cat.net

Abstract—Next-generation networks have become key enablers for distributed eXtended Reality (XR) services, which pose stringent demands in terms of bandwidth, compute and reliability. In this context, the Network as a Service (NaaS) paradigm, where the network offers APIs tailored to specific vertical domains, is a promising approach to enhance delivery protocols and communications for XR services. In this paper, we present NetXRate which is a new NaaS API tailored to interactive XR services. NetXRate leverages Open RAN (O-RAN) and the network exposure capabilities of the 5GCore, to deliver rate recommendations to XR applications based on the instantaneous capacity available in the cellular network. Using a simulative approach, we demonstrate how NetXRate can be integrated with two state-of-the-art Over-the-Top (OTT) XR rate recommendation strategies, achieving a reduction of up to 72% in outage probability in scenarios with severe network congestion where multiple XR users compete for higher share of bandwidth in the same cell.

I. INTRODUCTION

EXtended Reality (XR) is considered one of the most promising service classes for 5G and 6G cellular communications [1]. XR services are highly demanding in terms of bandwidth, compute, [2], and require interoperability across Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and application providers in order to be effectively deployed at scale within an MNO.

To address the challenges set by XR services, 3GPP started to define a set of network extensions devoted to enhance the performance of XR services, both at the architectural and at the Radio Access Network (RAN) levels in Release 16 [3]. At the architectural level, some of the proposed extensions include: i) *support for multi-modality flows*, enabling the 5G network to provide differentiated treatment to the various flows that conform a single media session; ii) *information exposure* towards the XR application functions, including the notification of congestion by means of Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN) markings, or API-based information exposure through the Network Exposure Function (NEF) and the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), and iii) *QoS handling at the level of Packet Data Unit (PDU) sets*, which enables the network to identify packets belonging to the same media segment, and therefore demand a correlated treatment. At the RAN level, current XR extensions include enhancements to align the sleep cycles of User Equipment (UE) for power saving purposes and adjusting the packet generation intervals used in the XR services.

Despite the recent advances being proposed in 3GPP, media services that are delivered over public cellular networks still

operate in an OTT fashion, where the mobile network is simply used as a data pipe. Under the OTT paradigm, critical control plane operations of the media service, such as the rate adaptation of the media flow, are performed solely relying on end-to-end measurements between the application client and backend components. Relevant streaming protocols that follow this model are Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) and HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) [4], which rely on throughput and/or buffer occupancy estimations at the client side to select the most appropriate rate from the server side. Despite the success of these streaming protocols, network-assisted approaches such as the Server and Network Assisted DASH (SAND) standard [5] have been proposed to enhance the streaming performance when multiple clients are active. A fundamental drawback of client-driven OTT approaches is that by relying on individual end-to-end measurements, clients compete with each other without being aware of the instantaneous capacity available in the network. Therefore, in dense wireless network scenarios, there is a crucial need for network-assisted rate control approaches to avoid frequent outages [6]. This is further interactive XR services, like holographic communications [2], in which the buffering delays need to be minimised and providing an uninterrupted and smooth playback process is a dominant requirement. Hence, the application and the network need to cooperate to fulfil the stringent latency and stability requirements of XR services. However, this approach remains in its infancy in the context of XR and public MNOs.

Cooperation between application functions (AFs) and the public mobile network is the core concept behind the NaaS paradigm, where the network acts as a platform offering cross-MNO APIs to the service developers. Following this view, the GSMA Open Gateway initiative [7] has standardised a first set of APIs tailored to several vertical domains, from which a Quality on Demand (QoD) API that can be used by XR service developers to guarantee performance is remarked [8]. A drawback of the QoD API, though, is that it prioritises traffic from a given AF over the rest of best-effort traffic in the same cell, and therefore it is less effective when multiple XR sessions are active in the same cell. To address this problem, we present the contribution of this paper in threefold:

- i. We present NetXRate, a novel NaaS API that provides explicit rate recommendations to XR AFs.

- ii. We derive NetXRRate xApp as a novel architecture combining O-RAN, NWDAF and NEF capabilities, and provides explicit rate recommendations to XR AF. Such NetXRRate recommendations can be complementary to the rate control strategies of OTT mechanisms to enhance stability of XR services.
- iii. We implement NetXRRate in a network level simulator(ns3), and demonstrate how it reduces outage probability up to a 60% and a 72% for two different OTT XR rate adaptation strategies, in scenarios with severe network congestion due to multiple XR users competing for the same resources.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the design of the proposed NetXRRate solution, and Section III benchmarks its performance. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. NETXRATE DESIGN

A. NetXRRate Architecture

Figure. 1 depicts the architecture of NetXRRate (bottom figure), as compared to the current approach employed by OTT services (upper figure).

Looking at the upper part of Figure 1, it depicts the XR service components both at the UE and at the backend sides, where the XR service is composed by a User Plane (UP) function (XR UP) that transmits the media segments and by a Control Plane function (XR CP) that embeds a rate control algorithm that controls and recommends adjustments to the transmission process. Client-side measurements are typically used to drive the decisions of the rate control function. These measurements may include: i) buffer estimations, ii) throughput estimations, or iii) combinations of the above [4]. These strategies can slowly track the fluctuating capacity of a cellular network, as changes in network capacity lead to corresponding variations in the measured variables. In addition, the greedy competition for resources between active devices in a cell, coupled with the lack of coordination among them, leads to inefficient sharing of the available network capacity [6].

To address the previous problem, we propose the NetXRRate architecture depicted in the bottom part of Figure 1. The key innovation of NetXRRate lies in its ability to allow the rate control function of the XR service to subscribe to explicit rate recommendations directly from the network. This subscription is facilitated through the NEF, which is a part of 5GCore. The NetXRRate rate recommendations are with a configurable interval, and each recommendation should be understood as the maximum capacity for that session available at a given time. Thus, NetXRRate is not meant to replace the OTT rate control algorithm but to complement it by making the NetXRRate recommendation a maximum cap on the data rate recommended by the XR rate control function, i.e., the XR rate with NetXRRate is computed as $\min(OTT_{rate}, NetXRRate_{rate})$.

To derive accurate estimations of the available network capacity, NetXRRate relies on the O-RAN architecture, where it deploys a NetXRRate xApp in the near-real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (nrt-RIC). Leveraging the O-RAN E2 service models, the NetXRRate xApp quickly tracks the capacity available to each

of the XR users active in the cell and computes a recommended capacity for each user. The NetXRRate xApp is described in detail in Section II-C. Finally, an architectural solution is needed to connect the recommendations generated by the NetXRRate xApp with the NEF function in the 5GCore. To this end, NetXRRate leverages the NWDAF, which can subscribe to an O-RAN xApp using the O-RAN Y1 interface [9].

Fig. 1. Proposed NetXRRate architectural components

B. NetXRRate signalling messages

First, the XR rate control function of the XR_AF_Server declares to the NEF the required uplink (UL)/downlink (DL) data rates for a given PDU session, identified using an IP address as shown in Figure 2. The NEF forwards the request to a module in the NWDAF deployed for the purpose of maintaining NetXRRate recommendations. The NWDAF module first discovers the cell where the target UE is connected by means of the Location Reporting APIs offered by the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF). Armed with the UE's serving cell, the NWDAF module can then identify the instance of the NetXRRate xApp that will handle the UE of interest. Each instance of the NetXRRate xApp is expected to handle only a limited number of cells. Before forwarding the request to the selected NetXRRate xApp, the NWDAF module maps the IP address provided by the NEF to a RAN identifier (RANID) by using the services exposed by the AMF since the NetXRRate xApp understands only RANIDs. Then, the NetXRRate xApp initiates a subscription request to the Distributed Unit (DU) handling the target cell, requesting a set of E2 Key Performance Measurement (KPM) counters [10], which are fed to the algorithm described in section II-C to derive a recommended rate for each XR UE present in the cell. Finally, those rate recommendations are reported back through the aforementioned network elements until they reach the XR rate control function, which uses the provided recommendation to limit the maximum rate used by the XR user plane function.

Fig. 2. Detailed interfaces and signalling messages used among the NetXrate components

A crucial parameter of NetXRate is the rate recommendation periodicity, which could be fine-adjusted based on the target requirements. The impact of this parameter will be studied in Section III.

C. NetXRate xApp

The goal of the NetXRate xApp is to generate rate recommendations. The NetXRate xApp needs to estimate the capacity that the scheduler will allocate to each XR user in the cell. To do that, the NetXRate xApp should be linked to the MAC scheduler implemented in the DU driving that cell. In the design of NetXRate, a proportional fair (PF) scheduler is considered in the DU, which is a common approach in practice [11].

The NetXRate xApp should have the same information as the PF scheduler, but this is challenging since the NetXRate xApp resides in the nrt-RIC while the PF scheduler is in the DU. To derive the information required by the NetXRate xApp to operate, the E2-KPM service model is used. In particular, the NetXRate xApp uses the following inputs:

- i The required data rate in bps provided by the NWDAF for the i th XR UE active in the cell at time t is $r_i(t)$.
- ii The maximum associated capacity available in the cell, i.e. $C_{max}(t)$ which is calculated using the maximum Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) that can be obtained from the configuration parameters of the cell through the E2 interface.
- iii The effective data rate $R_i(t)$ received at the i th UE at time

t when using the minimum MCS in the last window of τ seconds to track the time variability of the data rate. The reason for using the minimum MCS is to avoid having provided recommendations that exceed the overall cell capacity. The MCS statistics for each UE in the cell are obtained using the E2 KPM service model.

With such previous information, the NetXRate xApp derives the recommended capacity for each XR UE in the cell using the procedure described in Algorithm 1:

- i First, for each XR UE active in the cell, the effective data rate share is $\eta_i(t) = \frac{R_i(t)}{C_{max}(t)}$. Accordingly, the weighted required XR rate per UE is $w_i(t) = \frac{r_i(t)}{\eta_i(t)}$. This value captures the fact that XR UEs with lower MCS consume more radio resources.
- ii Then, a water-filling algorithm [11], with inputs $C_{max}(t)$ and $w_i(t)$, is used to generate an initial per UE capacity assignment, i.e., $u_i(t)$, such that $\sum_i u_i(t) = C_{max}(t)$.
- iii Finally, each obtained $u_i(t)$ is scaled by its associated $\eta_i(t)$, accounting for the fact that UEs are not operating at the maximum MCS, to obtain the recommended rate per UE as $\Theta_i(t+1) = u_i(t) \times \eta_i(t)$.

The computed rate recommendations $\Theta_i(t+1)$ are then periodically reported to the XR AF. For the sake of simplicity of the expressions, the time t is removed in the following algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: NetXRate xApp algorithm

Input : N number of UEs with required rate r_i , R_i ,
 C_{max} where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$.
Output : NetXRate recommendation Θ_i

- 1 Calculate $\eta_i = \frac{R_i}{C_{max}}$;
- 2 Obtain $w_i = \frac{r_i}{\eta_i}$;
- 3 Apply waterfilling algorithm to obtain f and u_i ;
- 4 Set $f_0 = 0$ and $n = 0$;
- 5 **while** $f_n \neq f_{n-1}$ **do**
- 6 $n = n + 1$;
- 7 **if** $f_n \geq w_i$ **then**
- 8 $U_n \leftarrow w_i$;
- 9 **else**
- 10 $O_n \leftarrow w_i$;
- 11 **end**
- 12 $f_n \leftarrow \frac{C_{max} - \sum_{i \in U_n} w_i}{|O_n|}$;
- 13 $f \leftarrow f_n$;
- 14 $U \leftarrow U_n$;
- 15 **end**
- 16 $U = \{u_1, \dots, u_N\}$;
- 17 Calculate the NetXRate recommendation;
- 18 Return $\Theta_i = u_i \times \eta_i$;

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section we evaluate the performance gains that NetXRate provides when compared to two state-of-the-art OTT rate adaptation strategies, which are introduced in Section III-A. Then, Section III-B describes our evaluation setup, and Sections III-C and III-D summarize the results of the performed evaluations.

A. OTT XR rate adaptation strategies

To benchmark NetXRate against the sole use of state-of-the-art OTT approaches, two different XR rate adaptation strategies are selected, referred to as the *PacketSize* and the *Inter Packet Arrival (IPA)* strategies. These strategies are introduced in [12] and have been designed using the 3GPP XR traffic models.

Both strategies adapt the effective media rate in the same manner. If more than 10% of media segments arriving at a UE playback buffer are late, the effective data rate is reduced by half. Conversely, if less than 2% of the media segments are late, the effective data rate is increased by 10%. These adaptations occur within a measurement window of 0.5 seconds. For both rate control strategies, a target data rate and frames per second (fps) are configured according to the application. The difference between the two strategies is that in the *PacketSize* strategy the effective data rate is controlled by adjusting the packet size at the media source while always keeping the same fps. while in the *IPA* strategy, the packet size is kept constant and the effective rate is controlled by adjusting the packet generation interval.

For each strategy, the client side is modelled using a playback buffer of maximum size 1 second that starts reproducing media

segments after a fixed initial delay, configured to be 240 milliseconds.

As described in Section II, NetXRate can be applied to these two strategies simply by using the recommendation to limit the maximum rate recommended by each OTT strategy.

B. Evaluation setup

To evaluate NetXRate, we use a simulative approach based on the ns-3 5G-LENA network simulator [13]. The NetXRate xApp is implemented and applied to the XR traffic models described earlier.

Our reference scenario consists of a public 5G network in an urban environment, operating at the 3.5GHz band with a 100MHz bandwidth and a 60kHz subcarrier spacing, where we use the Urban Macro propagation channel defined in 3GPP TR38.900. We consider a frame size of 10 ms and a TDD pattern of 7 downlink slots, 2 uplink slots, and 1 special slot. As MAC schedulers, we use proportional fairness (PF) with a fairness index of 1. % (i.e., traditional 3GPP PF).

To benchmark NetXRate, we consider a single 5G NR cell with a growing number of UEs performing XR sessions. We define a cluster consisting of six UEs organised into three groups that have different application and wireless channel characteristics. Group 1 consists of UEs receiving media flows of 6 Mbps and 30 frames per second (fps) while enjoying good radio conditions (MCS28). Group 2 consists of UEs receiving media flows of 12Mbps and 60fps, also under good radio conditions (MCS28). Finally, group 3 consists of UEs receiving media flows of 18 Mbps and 90 fps, which are located farther away from the base station and experience a variable MCS (MCS-6 to MCS-26). The value of the window τ is set to 0.2s. Unless otherwise stated, we configure NetXRate with a reporting period of 200 ms.

To achieve statistically meaningful results, we average the results of multiple independent simulation runs, where each run simulates a 30-second period.

C. Benchmarking NetXRate scalability

To assess the gains provided by NetXRate, we increase the number of UE clusters defined in our scenario until channel saturation is achieved. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) depict respectively the outage and the throughput experienced by the *PacketSize* and *IPA* XR rate adaptation strategies when using NetXRate and when using the default OTT rate control function.

The outage is defined as the percentage of time within a simulation run where the playback buffer in a UE is empty. A 10-second interval is used to measure outage samples from each UE, which are averaged and shown in Figure 3(a). Hence, a 20% outage in Figure 3(a) represents that a UE is in outage for a total of 2 seconds during a 10-second sample.

We can see in Figure 3(a) how outage naturally grows for all strategies as the number of clusters increases; however, when applying NetXRate, both the *PacketSize* and *IPA* rate adaptation strategies experience a much lower outage. In particular, in our considered scenario, NetXRate is able to reduce the outage probability up to 60% for the *PacketSize* strategy and up to

(a) Outage (% of time with buffer stall)

(b) Throughput over the wireless channel (dashed) and after the playback buffer (solid)

Fig. 3. Impact of growing number of clusters in NetXRRate and OTT rate adaptation

72% for the *IPA* strategy. The reason why NetXRRate is able to reduce outage probability is that by limiting the media source rate according to the instantaneous channel capacity, network overloads are largely avoided. These overloads appear in OTT strategies when multiple UEs running their rate control algorithms independently request a large data rate at the same time exceeding the available capacity. Using the NetXRRate recommendations, even when being at the maximum rate allowed by the rate control algorithm, the aggregate requests of the XR UEs in the same cell should not exceed the aggregate cell capacity. Notice though that, although reduced, overload situations may still occur under NetXRRate due to inaccuracies in the MCS estimation process (c.f. Section II-C). As a future work, a full characterisation of the nature of the outage events in NetXRRate in terms of duration and distribution across UEs is to be considered.

Figure 3(b) depicts, for each XR rate adaptation strategy, the throughput measured over the wireless channel (dashed bars) and the aggregated throughput measured after the playback buffer of each UE (solid bars). Notice that for a given rate adaptation strategy, the difference between the dashed and the solid bars represents wasted throughput that has been transmitted over the wireless channel but has not arrived in time to be played in the playback buffer of the UE. By adapting the media rate at the source according to the estimated wireless capacity, NetXRRate increases the useful throughput up to 30% for the *PacketSize* strategy and up to 25% for the *IPA* strategy, with respect to the OTT approach. The results in Figure 3(b) demonstrate that explicitly allocating capacity for each XR session in a centralised way, as done by NetXRRate, significantly enhances the efficiency of the network. The reason why NetXRRate does not manage to completely avoid wasted throughput is that it sometimes overestimates network capacity due to inaccuracies in the process of estimating the MCS used by each UE (c.f. Section II-C).

Based on the described results, NetXRRate is proved to be effective at enhancing the quality of XR sessions, independently of the OTT rate adaptation function being used by the XR service.

D. Impact of NetXRRate recommendation period

A key parameter in the design of NetXRRate is the period at which updated rate recommendations are provided to the XR media source. Figures 4(a) and 4(b) depict, respectively, the outage and throughput experienced by the NetXRRate strategies when increasing the period parameter between 200 ms and 5 seconds for the case of 4 clusters.

The main finding from Figure 4 is that, in our scenarios, NetXRRate slightly improves when increasing the period value from 200ms to 500ms, while remaining fairly constant for periods above 500ms. The reason for this behaviour is related to the per-UE MCS estimation approach used in the NetXRRate xApp (c.f. Section II-C). To generate a per-UE capacity allocation for the next period, the NetXRRate xApp needs to assume a MCS value for each UE. The main design principle in our current implementation is to avoid exceeding the overall cell capacity. Hence, we use a heuristic that assumes for the next period the worst-case MCS observed in the current period. In our considered scenarios, this heuristic turns out to be too optimistic when the interval is low (200 ms), as we may have cases where the UE does not experience low MCSs during the current observation period. As we increase the period, the likelihood of experiencing a low MCS increases, resulting in more conservative recommendations. The MCS estimation approach used in the NetXRRate xApp is thus a key element in our architecture. As future work, the investigation of more complex estimators based on AI/ML could be proposed.

These results in Figure 4 demonstrate that in a situation with moderate mobility, as the one considered in our evaluation, rate recommendations in the order of seconds are enough to

(a) Outage (% of time with buffer stall)

(b) Throughput over the wireless channel (dashed) and after the playback buffer (solid)

Fig. 4. Impact of NetXRRate recommendation period in NetXRRate and OTT rate adaptation

reap the benefits of NetXRRate, which ensures the viability of NetXRRate when applied to real networks.

IV. CONCLUSION

An excellent delivery of XR services is a key design objective for next-generation mobile networks. XR services often require interactivity and are thus very demanding in terms of bandwidth, compute, and reliability. To serve this and other stringent verticals, the NaaS paradigm offers novel APIs that allow the AF to cooperate tightly with the network to enhance the performance of the communication service.

In this paper we have proposed NetXRRate, which is a novel NaaS API that provides rate recommendations to XR AFs. NetXRRate leverages the O-RAN architecture and the exposure capabilities of the 5G Core. The NetXRRate recommendations are adjusted to the instantaneous capacity available in the network and can be integrated with any existent OTT rate control algorithm. We have evaluated NetXRRate using a simulative approach, demonstrating a reduction of up to 72% in outage probability when integrated with two state-of-the-art OTT rate control functions in scenarios where multiple XR users compete in the same cell.

As future work, NetXRRate needs to evolve in two main ways. First, the NetXRRate xApp needs to consider scenarios of high mobility, where per UE MCS predictions are more challenging, and scenarios where best-effort users interact with XR users in the same cell. Second, hybrid strategies should be studied where the NetXRRate rate recommendations are combined with a prioritised treatment for the XR traffic, such as the one provided by the CAMARA QoD API [8].

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union – NextGeneration EU, in the framework of the Recovery Plan, Transformation and Resilience (PRTR) (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021, Ref. TSI-063000-2021-2 – 6G-Openverso-Net), and

by the Horizon Europe (Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking) program, under agreement n° 101096838 (6G-XR project). The work of Mario Montagud has been funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 under Grant RYC2020-030679-I and by “the European Social Fund (ESF) Investing in Your Future”.

REFERENCES

- [1] Minopoulos, Georgios *et al.*, “Opportunities and challenges of tangible XR applications for 5G networks and beyond,” *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, 2022.
- [2] G. C. S. Fernández, M. Montagud and D. Rincón, “Multiparty Holomeetings: Toward a New Era of Low-Cost Volumetric Holographic Meetings in Virtual Reality,” *Ieee Access*, vol. 10, pp. 81856–81876, 2022.
- [3] 3GPP, TR26.928, “Extended Reality (XR) in 5G,” Tech. Rep. v.16.1.0, 2020.
- [4] Kua, Jonathan *et al.*, “A Survey of Rate Adaptation Techniques for Dynamic Adaptive Streaming Over HTTP,” *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1842–1866, 2017.
- [5] Thomas, Emmanuel *et al.*, “Enhancing MPEG DASH Performance via Server and Network Assistance,” *SMPTE Motion Imaging Journal*, vol. 126, no. 1, pp. 22–27, 2017.
- [6] Catalan-Cid, Miguel *et al.*, “FALCON: Joint Fair Airtime Allocation and Rate Control for DASH Video Streaming in Software Defined Wireless Networks,” in *Proc. NOSSDAV '20*, (New York, NY, USA), p. 14–20, 2020.
- [7] GSMA, “GSMA Open Gateway.” <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/gsma-open-gateway/>, 2023.
- [8] Ordonez-Lucena, Jose *et al.*, “Pathways towards Network-as-a-Service: The CAMARA Project,” in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGCOMM Workshop on Network-Application Integration*, NAI '22, p. 53–59, Association for Computing Machinery, 2022.
- [9] ORAN WG3: Near-real-time RIC and E2 Interface Workgroup, “O-RAN Near-RT RIC Architecture 5.0.” <https://orandownloadsweb.azurewebsites.net/specifications>, Reterived: December 2023.
- [10] ORAN WG3: Near-real-time RIC and E2 Interface Workgroup, “O-RAN E2 Service Model (E2SM) KPM 4.0.” <https://orandownloadsweb.azurewebsites.net/specifications>, Reterived: December 2023.
- [11] M.-R. t. Hojeij, “Waterfilling-based proportional fairness scheduler for downlink non-orthogonal multiple access,” *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 230–233, 2017.
- [12] Lagen, Sandra *et al.*, “QoS Management for XR Traffic in 5G NR: A Multi-Layer System View & End-to-End Evaluation,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, pp. 1–7, 2023.
- [13] “5G-LENA.” <https://5g-lena.cttc.es/>, 2023.